

EXPRESSIVE PRODUCTION OF PIANO TIMBRE: TOUCH AND PLAYING TECHNIQUES FOR TIMBRE CONTROL IN PIANO PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Timbre is an essential expressive parameter in piano performance. Advanced-level pianists have integrated the palette of timbres at their artistic disposal as abstract concepts and multimodal images. A correspondingly imaged vocabulary composed of various adjectival descriptors is used in discussing and designating precise timbral nuances. However, the actual means of production and control of timbral nuances at the piano are not always explicitly expressed. This study explores the precise performance parameters used in producing different timbral nuances. For this aim, four short pieces were composed. Each was performed by four pianists, who highlighted five timbral nuances most representative of the piano timbre-describing vocabulary: dry, bright, round, velvety and dark. The performances were recorded with the Bösendorfer CEUS system, a high-quality piano equipped with high-accuracy sensors and an embedded computer. Fine-grained performance features were extracted from the data collected. The features that significantly differed between different-timbre performances were identified. The performance space resulting from a principal component analysis revealed an average organization of timbral nuances along a circular arc. Thirteen essential, timbre-discriminating performance features were selected. Detailed descriptions were thus obtained for each timbral nuance, according to the fine characteristics of their production and control in piano performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Musical performance is essential to the art and experience of music. Classical performers in particular will apply their expressive creativity towards enlightening a composition. An extensive, empiric body of knowledge was thus developed amongst musicians to best serve the art and technique of performance, for every instrument, and especially in the context of this article, for the piano.

Among the many expressive musical attributes available to pianists, timbre has been widely acknowledged within the pianistic community [1]. Beyond its widely-understood

function as a characteristic inherent to an instrument or sound source, timbre is also envisioned by pianists as a refined quality of sound, over which they hold control by way of expressive nuances in their performances. As such, pianists believe in their ability to produce different timbral nuances that can suit their expressive intentions [2]. This palette of piano timbre nuances has been associated with an extensive vocabulary, which includes numerous adjectival descriptors that pianists use to convey a precise conception of a timbral nuance [3, 4]. However, the precise technique and ways of production of piano timbre nuances has generally been subdued to abstraction, mental conception, imitation and aural modelling [5] in piano pedagogy and treatises [6, 7].

Moreover, scientific studies on piano performance and timbre production concluded long ago that piano timbre control would be limited by the mechanical constraints of the action to sheer keystroke velocity, thus making timbre inseparable from intensity [8]. However, when instead of considering a single, isolated key, the subtleties of tone combinations involved in a polyphonic musical context are taken into account, expressive piano performance parameters (such as articulation, synchrony and dynamic differentiation between tones, and pedalling) become involved in governing the emergence of performer-controlled composite timbres. Then, in order to measure and quantify piano performance with the level of precision at which the subtle nuances of timbre production can be identified, high-accuracy piano performance-recording tools are required. While extensive scientific research on piano performance has made use of MIDI digital recording pianos (and before that, mechanical apparatus such as piano rolls [9] and embedded cameras [10]) and acoustical analysis to learn more about specific technical aspects and general expressive models of piano performance [11], the intricacies of timbre production have essentially remained out of the reach and/or concern of piano performance studies. Yet in a notable exception, Ortmann investigated the relations between piano touch and timbre on a single tone [12]. He associated, to several 'tone-qualities' (each described by an adjectival descriptor), precise key depression profiles aimed at highlighting the key velocity and touch percussiveness from which could stem the tone-quality.

This study aims at following in these steps, by systematically investigating the strategies and technical nuances of gestural control involved in pianists' use of timbre as an

expressive device in piano performance. With the high-accuracy Bösendorfer CEUS digital piano performance-recording system, the study explores piano timbre production in a polyphonic, ecologically valid musical context.

2. METHOD

In order to explore the expressive production of piano timbre nuances in a musically relevant framework that could mirror a genuine musical experience, the study was designed with respect to the following steps: selection of the most relevant verbal descriptors of piano timbre to designate the timbral nuances to explore; conception of musical pieces to be expressively performed according to these different timbral nuances; use of non-invasive, high-accuracy piano performance-recording equipment; timbre-coloured performance recordings; and extraction therein of meaningful piano performance and touch descriptors.

2.1 Piano timbre descriptors

The verbalization of piano timbre was studied quantitatively [13], according to judgements of semantic similarity between the 14 descriptors of piano timbre most cited by pianists in [3]. These evaluations were mapped into a semantic space, whose first two, most salient dimensions formed a plan in which descriptors were grouped in five distinct clusters — which was confirmed by hierarchical cluster analysis. In each cluster, the descriptor judged the most familiar was selected. The five most familiar, diverse and representative timbre descriptors thus highlighted — **Dry, Bright, Round, Velvety** and **Dark** — appear (in that order) along a circular arc in the semantic plan.

These five descriptors defined the timbres for which to seek out the production patterns in piano performances.

2.2 Musical pieces

In order to set a musical context adequate to expressive timbre production in performances, four short solo piano pieces were selected, among 15 specially composed for the study following instructions on the timbral nuances to be expressed (cf. Figure 1). Each selected piece could allow for a meaningful, consistent-throughout expression of each of the five timbral nuances, and featured many aspects of piano technique that we wanted to explore. Each just a few bars long (from four to seven, with different meters), their duration at score tempo ranged between 12 and 15 seconds.

2.3 Equipment

To investigate the fine-grained nuances of pianists' performance control and touch that let them express different timbral nuances, highly precise data were required, from which to thoroughly assess the intricacies of key strokes. In this aim, we had the opportunity to use the Bösendorfer CEUS piano digital recording system. Equipped with optical sensors behind the keys, hammers and pedals, microprocessors, electronic boards (cf. Figure 2), and a computer system, the CEUS system can track key and pedal positions and hammer velocities at high resolution (8-bit)

Figure 1. Scores of the four pieces composed and selected for the study.

and high sampling rate (500 Hz). The system we used was embedded in the Imperial Bösendorfer Model 290 grand piano installed at BRAMS.

The CEUS recording system constitutes an extremely precise tool to measure the subtleties in pianists' touch, in finer detail than was ever accessible to mechanical or MIDI piano performance-recording systems.

2.4 Performances

Four pianists¹ participated in the study. Each participant had received in advance the pieces scores and timbral nuances to explore, and were given time to practice. Rehearsal sessions were allotted on the Bösendorfer piano, to allow for familiarization with the instrument and the room. They were then asked to perform each of the four pieces, with each of the five timbres. Three such runs of 20 perfor-

¹ One female, three male; one Canadian, two French, one Italian; age from 22 to 46; all had extensive professional experience and advanced-level piano performance diploma. They are further referred to by their initials: PL, RB, BB and FP.

Figure 2. Details of the CEUS system: fallboard display interface and embedded electronics (©L.Bösendorfer Klavierfabrik GmbH).

manances were conducted successively so as to get three performances for each condition (piece \times timbre). Each of the 60 performances per participant was recorded through the CEUS system. We thus collected 240 CEUS `boe`-format recordings of 4 pianists performing 4 pieces with 5 different timbres, 3 times each.

2.5 Performance analysis

In order to extract meaningful piano performance and touch features from CEUS-acquired data, a `MatLab` toolbox was specifically developed [14]. From the high-frequency, high-resolution key/pedal positions and hammer velocities, note and chord structures were retrieved, and an exhaustive set of quantified features spanning several broad areas of piano performance and touch were computed for each note (46 features) and chord (168 features²): dynamic levels; attack speed, depth, type, percussiveness and synchrony; sustain, release durations and synchrony (within chords); articulation, intervals and overlaps (between chords); and detailed use of pedals. Averages and deviations per performance (overall, and for the left and right hands separately) were calculated for all features, so as to enable comparisons between performances expressing different timbral nuances. In total, $322 \times 3 = 966$ features were calculated to characterize each of the 240 recorded performances.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Significant, timbre-discriminating piano performance features

Statistical analyses of variance were performed over this 966-features-by-240-performance dataset. The data was organized in a repeated-measures design, with 80 samples (one for each same-pianist, same-piece, same-timbre condition, which includes 3 performances), timbre as factor (five groups) and the performance features as dependent variables. Different tests of analysis of variance (repeated-measures ANOVA, Welch robust test of equality of means, Kruskal-Wallis rank analysis) were performed, depending on the assumptions respected for each feature.

In the end, amongst the 966 performance features, 192 proved significant at the 5% level³ in rejecting the null hypothesis of equal variance between the five timbre groups.

² Including the means and standard deviations between the notes constituent of the chord, plus its chord-specific features.

³ Including 145 features significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$) and 83

Figure 3. Principal Component Analysis over 80 samples (3-repetition performance means) for 192 significant features. Coloured crosses and ellipses indicate averages per timbre and ± 1 S.E. (resp.).

3.2 Performance spaces of piano timbre

Principal Component Analysis was applied to the subset of 192 significant performance features. The first two principal components — which combined explained 53.1% of the variance in the input dataset (34.63% + 18.47% resp.) — and the position of each performance⁴ according to their coordinates in these two dimensions, are represented in Figure 3. In this performance space, the five mean positions of performances sharing the same timbre appear along a circular arc. This arrangement of the five timbres is mostly consistent with their arrangement in the semantic similarity space [13], yet with an inversion of order along the arc of timbral nuances Dark and Velvety.

Scattering effects of performances can be observed, imputable to each of the three experimental factors. Performances tend to be grouped by performer (most especially for BB's, concentrated in the upper right region) and by piece (essentially in interaction with timbre). Yet the most salient grouping effect is due to timbre. A timbre-by-timbre account of performance positions shows that all Dry-timbre performances are situated on the left side of the space (mostly bottom-left), while most Velvety-timbre performances are positioned on the far-right side. Bright, Round and Dark-timbre performances are closely scattered around their respective means, except for one outlier among Bright performances and two outliers among Dark performances.⁵ The loadings (weights attributed to each performance feature) for dimensions 1 and 2 do not show any predominant weight associated to one or a few features, yet they reveal that dimension 1 represents above all the dynamics, attack and soft pedal features, while dimension 2 mostly represents sustain pedal features.

features significant at the 0.1% level ($p < 10^{-3}$).

⁴ For the sake of display clarity, only the 80 means over the three same-pianist, same-piece, same-timbre repetitions are plotted, instead of the complete 240-performance set.

⁵ Outliers are defined according to 95% confidence intervals, *i.e.* more than 1.96 standard deviations apart from the mean.

PCA performance spaces were also produced and studied separately for each piece and each performer. In each case, the first two principal components accounted for more than half of the variance in the input datasets, and the corresponding planar spaces all showed the same organization of five mean positions of same-timbre performances along a circular arc. However, the PCA loadings differed between cases, as different groups of features were most represented in the two dimensions depending on the piece or the performer.

Overall, the production of each timbral nuance was shown in the performance spaces as fairly consistent between performers (and between same-performers repetitions). However, this consistency was less salient for timbres Dry and Velvety, and could be affected by the scattering effects due to pieces and performers.

3.3 Characterization of piano timbre production

In order to obtain a minimal, unique performance portrait for each of the five piano timbre nuances explored in this study, the set of 192 significant features was reduced to 13 essential features. In this aim, the 192 features were divided into four broad, technically independent categories: (1) dynamics/attack, (2) soft pedal, (3) sustain pedal, and (4) articulation. Correlations between features were sought out within each group. The correlations coefficients were then submitted to cluster analysis. For each category, an optimal and meaningful number of clusters was empirically defined. With regards to pianistic/technical meaning, the most statistically significant feature was conserved in each cluster. This allowed us to identify, with hardly any loss of relevant information, a minimal set of 13 performance features to adequately describe each of the five timbral nuances in a unique way. These results are presented in the Kiviart (radar) chart of Figure 4. Below are the descriptions and statistical scores⁶ of these 13 most relevant features.

- **Hammer velocity** ($\chi^2(4) = 23.195, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.294$ overall; $\chi^2(4) = 20.935, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.265$ left hand; $\chi^2(4) = 25.156, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.318$ right hand): maximum hammer velocity for each note, as directly measured by the piano sensors. As a direct correlate to intensity, it makes for a descriptor of dynamic level.
- **Key depression depth** ($\chi^2(4) = 21.412, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.271$): indicates how deep (close to the keyboard) the key gets depressed for each note.
- **Variations in key attack speed** ($F(4, 75) = 3.117, p = 0.02$, effect size $r = 0.062$): indicate which timbres present the largest ranges in attack speed.
- **Attack duration** ($F(4, 75) = 3.881, p = 0.006$, effect size $r = 0.133$ overall; $F(4, 75) = 3.591, p = 0.01$, effect size $r = 0.149$ left hand; $F(4, 75) = 3.432, p = 0.012$, effect size $r = 0.105$ right hand): durations of note attacks, from the start of key depression

⁶ Depending on the adequate statistical test as dictated by the assumptions met, the statistic reported can be the ANOVA F-ratio $F(df1, df2)$, the Welch F-ratio $F_W(df1, df2)$ or the Kruskal-Wallis Chi-square $\chi^2(df1)$.

Figure 4. Kiviart chart of the 13 performance features giving a minimal and unique description of the five timbral nuances explored in the study. Z-scores per timbral nuance for each feature are indicated with colour-coded dots. The five colour-coded, dot-linking closed lines portray each timbral nuance. Shades around each closed line shows the ± 1.96 S.E. intervals (95% confidence interval).

to the instant of hammer launch. While primarily inversely proportional to intensity (the faster the attack, the shorter its duration), it also depends on nuances of touch and articulation at note onsets.

- **Soft pedal depression** ($F_W(4, 110.994) = 4.629, p = 0.002$, effect size $r = 0.291$): its amount of depression along the performance.
- **Sustain pedal use** ($F(4, 75) = 9.916, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.315$): duration of sustain pedal depression during performances.
- **Sustain pedal depression** ($F_W(4, 116.114) = 7.727, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.438$): its amount of depression along the performance.
- **Release duration** ($F_W(4, 115.91) = 13.795, p < 10^{-3}$, effect size $r = 0.32$): time taken for key release. This mostly accounts for articulation: a note released slowly (thus slowed by the finger) may probably overlap with the next.
- **Right-hand chords overlap** ($F(4, 75) = 2.561, p = 0.045$, effect size $r = 0.111$): descriptor of right-hand articulation: the more overlap, the more *legato* in right-hand play.

Performance descriptions of the five timbral nuances were also assessed separately for each piece, according to the features significant for the piece. In each case, the piecewise performance portrayals of the five timbral nuances were obtained according to a subset of the same features as overall (or equivalent ones). This indicates that, although the technical and compositional characteristics of a piece can bear an influence upon the efficiency of performance features to differentiate between timbral nuances, there exists an overall frame of performance features from which timbral nuances can be portrayed.

Table 1. Summary of performance features significant in Post-hoc pairwise timbre comparisons.

Timbres		Significant descriptors pairwise	
Timbre #1	Timbre #2	Timbre #1 > Timbre #2	Timbre #1 < Timbre #2
Dry	Bright		Sustain pedal depression
Dry	Round		Sustain pedal use and depression
Dry	Dark		Right-hand attack duration
			Sustain pedal use and depression
			Left-hand chord durations
		Variations in right-hand overlap durations	Release durations
Dry	Velvety	Hammer velocity	
		Attack speed	Right-hand attack duration
		Key depression depth (esp. left hand)	
			Soft pedal depression
			Sustain pedal use and depression
			Release durations
Bright	Round	none	
Bright	Dark	Hammer velocity	
		Right-hand attack speed	Right-hand attack duration
		Key depression depth	
			Sustain pedal use
Bright	Velvety	Hammer velocity	
		Key attack speed	Right-hand attack duration
		Key depression depth	
			Soft pedal depression
Round	Dark	none	
Round	Velvety		Soft pedal depression
Dark	Velvety	none	

Furthermore, the evolution in time of those timbre-characteristic performance features were analyzed with regard to the musical structure of the pieces. Timbre profiles according to performance features were shown to follow certain patterns segmented per phrase/motif, with feature values either constantly increasing, decreasing or remaining stable along each phrase. At phrase transition, those patterns would either change in direction, remain the same, or be drastically reset (e.g. sustain pedal released at the end of a phrase). Such patterns would differ between timbres, in average feature value, in direction and amount of increase or decrease, in fluctuations within the phrases, and they especially differed in behaviour at phrase transitions.

3.4 Pairwise comparisons between timbres

The statistical analyses of variance were followed up by post-hoc pairwise comparisons, with Tukey’s Honest Significant Difference test to estimate features significance, in the aim of assessing which performance features most significantly differ between each of the ten timbre pairs. Those results, once reduced for each timbre pair to a set of non-redundant (both in meaning and values), significant features, are presented in Table 1. This description is consistent with the PCA performance space and the arrangement patterns of timbres, with Round in the middle, Dry and Bright at one end and Dark and Velvety at the other.

3.5 Summary: Description of piano timbre nuances production

Thus, in the light of an exhaustive exploration of piano performance and touch, the five timbral nuances examined in

this study could be portrayed according to the specificities of their production at the piano.

The production of each timbral nuance, as defined according to one verbal descriptor, could be characterized, in the context of this experiment, by a unique combination and pattern of utilization of certain control parameters:

- **Dry:** high intensity (slightly more with the left hand), very short and constantly fast attacks; keys are not fully depressed, which favours a very *staccato* articulation; both soft and sustain pedals are hardly used.
- **Bright:** high intensity (slight right-hand emphasis), very short attacks; keys deeply depressed down to the keybed; intermediate, *non-legato* articulation; the soft pedal is barely used; the sustain pedal is used sparingly, but is strongly depressed when in use.
- **Round:** the most average nuance in its production, with no salient trait: moderate, well-balanced, and constant intensity and attacks; key depressions are not very deep, yet well below escapement point; the soft pedal is barely used; the sustain pedal is used frequently and massively; and the articulation is quite *legato*.
- **Dark:** sharp contrast between hands in intensity and attack, very light in the right hand while much more marked in the bass, left hand; keys lightly depressed; fair use of the soft pedal; massive, quasi-constant use of the sustain pedal; and a very *legato* articulation, especially right-hand.
- **Velvety:** very low intensity, long attacks (especially with the right hand); very shallow key depression, very *legato* articulation (much more so in the left hand); prominent use of the soft and sustain pedals.

These features are overall characteristics of the production of each of the five timbral nuances examined in this study, independently of the performer and the musical context — as least to the extent of musical diversity represented in the four pieces composed for this study. Therefore, in the context of this study, the production and control of different timbral nuances in piano performance involved differences in dynamics, attack (and balance between hands), key depression depth, pedalling and articulation. On the other hand, the performance features of synchrony between notes in chords, note sustains, intervals between chords, and left-hand overlaps were not used in significantly different ways for producing each timbral nuance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In exploring the expressive production of piano timbre, this study has revealed the differences in the production of five timbral nuances described by the terms Dry, Bright, Round, Velvety and Dark, and has identified specific patterns in the precise control of fine-grained performance features, through nuances in intensity, attack, key depression depth, articulation and pedalling, that let those timbral nuances arise in expressive piano performance. This quantified understanding of piano timbre production and control ought to be envisioned as a complement to the empiric

body of knowledge that pianists have come to develop, both individually and as transmitted through teaching in a pedagogical context. With this study, the hope is to build a bridge between the pianistic and scientific perspectives on expressive piano performance and timbre production.

In complement to the study and results that were presented in this article, other related research questions are currently being investigated. First, the audio recordings of the performances are being used in perception tests, in order to determine whether the timbral nuances that the performers intended to express can be correctly identified. Acoustical analyses of the audio recordings will seek out the acoustical correlates of the piano timbre nuances performed. Correlations between the production and control patterns, the perceptual identification, and the acoustical correlates of piano timbre nuances will be examined, in particular to determine which performance features have an actual effect on sound production. Moreover, the individual strategies of expressive performance employed by each of the four participant pianists, overall and for producing the five different timbral nuances, are being explored.

In the future, this work could be applied to piano pedagogy. New methods could complement the traditional approach to piano timbre — through mental conception, imitation and careful self-actualization in performance as guided by the musical ear — with the devising of precise, tangible advice on the gesture to use in producing specific timbral nuances. Moreover, the results could be applied to the digital sound synthesis of piano timbre, and more precisely to the control of timbral nuances in piano synthesis engines. More subtle control parameters could be obtained — either with high-accuracy digital keyboard interfaces or with a software augmentation of the MIDI data sent by standard keyboard controllers — and used in conveying a more realistic simulation of an actual piano performance, coloured in timbre.

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Bernays, “Expression et production du timbre au piano selon les traités: Conception du timbre instrumental exprimée par les pianistes et professeurs dans les ouvrages à vocation pédagogique,” *Recherche en éducation musicale*, vol. 29, pp. 7–27, 2012.
- [2] G. Sandor, *On piano playing*. New York: Schirmer Books, 1995, (First edition: 1981).
- [3] M. Bellemare and C. Traube, “Verbal description of piano timbre: Exploring performer-dependent dimensions,” in *Digital proceedings of the second Conference on Interdisciplinary Musicology (CIM05)*. Montreal, QC: OICRM, 2005.
- [4] P. Cheminée, “«Vous avez dit «clair»? » le lexique des pianistes, entre sens commun et terminologie,” *Cahiers du LCPE: Dénomination, désignation et catégories*, vol. 7, pp. 39–54, 2006.
- [5] R. Woody, “The relationship between explicit planning and expressive performance of dynamic variations in an aural modeling task,” *Journal of Research in Music Education*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 331–342, 1999.
- [6] H. Neuhaus, *The art of piano playing*. London, UK: Barrie and Jenkins, 1973, translated from Russian by K.A. Leibovitch.
- [7] G. Kochevitsky, *The art of piano playing: A scientific approach*. Secaucus, NJ: Summy-Birchard, 1967.
- [8] H. Hart, M. Fuller, and W. Lusby, “A precision study of piano touch and tone,” *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. VI, pp. 80–94, 1934.
- [9] L. Vernon, “Synchronization of chords in artistic piano music,” in *Objective Analysis of Music Performance*, C. Seashore, Ed. Iowa City, IA: University of Iowa Press, 1936, pp. 307–345.
- [10] M. Henderson, J. Tiffin, and C. Seashore, “The Iowa piano camera and its use,” in *Objective Analysis of Music Performance*, C. Seashore, Ed. Iowa City, IA: University of Iowa Press, 1936, pp. 252–262.
- [11] W. Goebel, S. Dixon, G. DePoli, A. Friberg, R. Bresin, and G. Widmer, “‘Sense’ in expressive music performance: Data acquisition, computational studies, and models,” in *Sound to Sense — Sense to Sound: A State of the Art in Sound and Music Computing*, P. Polotti and D. Rocchesso, Eds. Berlin, Germany: Logos, 2008, pp. 195–242.
- [12] O. Ortmann, *The Physiological Mechanics of Piano Technique*. New York: E.P. Dutton, 1929.
- [13] M. Bernays and C. Traube, “Verbal expression of piano timbre: Multidimensional semantic space of adjectival descriptors,” in *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Performance Science (ISPS2011)*, A. Willmann, D. Edwards, and L. Bartel, Eds. Utrecht, Netherlands: European Association of Conservatoires, 2011, pp. 299–304.
- [14] ———, “Piano touch analysis: A MATLAB toolbox for extracting performance descriptors from high-resolution keyboard and pedalling data,” in *Proceedings of Journées d’Informatique Musicale (JIM2012), Gestes, Virtuosité et Nouveaux Medias*, T. Dutoit, T. Todoroff, and N. d’Alessandro, Eds. Mons, Belgium: UMONS/numediart, 2012, pp. 55–64.